

CONVERSIVE TRANSFORMATIONS IN LITERARY TRANSLATION

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ANNOTATSIYA. Ushbu maqolada badiiy tarjimada konversiv transformatsiyalardan foydalanish masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Konversiv munosabatdagi leksik birliklar tahlil qilinadi va ularning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari izohlanadi. Maqolada konversiv transformatsiyalarning boshqa modifikatsiyalar bilan o'zaro bog'liq munosabati tadqiq qilinadi.

Kalit soʻzlar: tarjima, konversiv tarjima, tarjima transformatsiyalari, konversiv transformatsiya, matnning diskursiv shakli.

АННОТАЦИЯ. В данной статье рассматривается использование конверсионных преобразований в художественном переводе. Анализируются лексические единицы в конверсионных отношениях и поясняются их особенности. В статье будет исследована взаимосвязь конверсионных преобразований с другими модификациями.

Ключевые слова: перевод, конверсионный перевод, переводческие трансформации, конверсивная трансформация, дискурсивная форма текста.

ABSTRACT. This article examines the use of conversion transformations in literary translation. Lexical units in the conversion relationship are analyzed and their specific features are explained. In the article interrelationship of conversion transformations with other modifications will be researched.

Key words: translation, conversion translation, translation transformations, conversive transformation, discursive form of the text.

Introduction

In the field of literary translation, the notion of conversive transformations has sparked significant scholarly interest due to its profound implications on the understanding and interpretation of translated texts. The process of translation involves a complex interplay of linguistic, cultural, and stylistic elements that require meticulous and thoughtful consideration. Translation scholars have long debated the extent to which a translated work can faithfully capture the essence and nuances of the original text, with some arguing that conversive transformations are inevitable in the process. By examining how translators navigate the challenges of preserving the tone, style, and cultural context of a text while also making it accessible to a new audience, we can gain insights into the innovative strategies employed in literary translation. This essay seeks to explore the concept of conversive transformations in depth, shedding light on the intricate dynamics at play in the realm of literary translation.

Conversive transformations in literary translation refer to the process by which elements of a source text are inverted or reversed in the target text to convey the same meaning in a different linguistic or cultural context. These transformations are essential in bridging the gap between two languages and cultures, as they allow for the preservation of the original message while adapting it to the new audience. One common example of conversive transformations is the reversal of word order or syntax to maintain the intended emphasis or emotional impact of the original text. Additionally, cultural references or idiomatic expressions may be modified to ensure they are comprehensible and relevant to the target audience. By carefully employing conversive transformations, translators can effectively convey the richness and nuances of the original text in a way that resonates with readers in the target language. Even though some may argue that these transformations dilute the authenticity of the source text, when done thoughtfully and skillfully, conversive transformations serve as a powerful tool in the art of literary translation.

In literary translation, the theoretical framework of conversive transformations serves as a crucial guide for understanding the intricate process of transferring meaning between languages. This framework posits that translations are not mere replicas of original texts but rather dynamic reimaginings that involve a series of conversive transformations. These transformations include shifts in linguistic structures, cultural references, and even narrative perspectives, all of which contribute to the creation of a new text that resonates with the target audience. By acknowledging the presence of these transformations, translators are able to navigate the complexities of cross-cultural communication and convey the essence of the original work in a way that is both faithful and relevant to the intended readers. A deep understanding of conversive transformations is essential for achieving successful literary translations that retain the spirit of the source text while adapting it to a new cultural context.¹

Conversive transformations in literary translation involve a complex interplay of linguistic and cultural elements that go beyond mere word-for-word substitutions. These transformations require the translator to navigate the nuances of both languages involved while also capturing the deeper meanings and intentions of the original text. According to Vandaele (2002), conversive transformations refer to the process by which a translator restructures the target text to convey a similar effect or message as the source text, with language-specific adjustments made to ensure coherence and fidelity. By understanding the concept of conversive transformations, translators can make more informed decisions about how to effectively convey the content and style of a literary work across languages. This process requires a delicate balance between remaining true to the original text and adapting it for a new audience or cultural context. Ultimately, conversive transformations serve as a bridge between languages, allowing readers to access and appreciate the richness of literature from different cultural backgrounds.²

¹ Laurence Raw, 2012-01-12

² Meredith J. C. Warren, 2019-05-03

The field of translation studies has long grappled with the nuanced concept of conversive transformations, which play a crucial role in the process of translating literary works. These transformations involve not only linguistic adjustments but also the intricate navigation of cultural nuances and literary devices to ensure the faithful rendition of the original text. Significantly, conversive transformations serve as a bridge between the source and target languages, allowing for the transmission of ideas, emotions, and cultural specificities across linguistic boundaries. Scholars have delved deep into the complexities of conversive transformations, highlighting their impact on the quality and authenticity of translated texts.

The factors influencing conversive transformations in literary translation are multifaceted and can vary depending on the linguistic, cultural, and contextual elements involved. One key consideration is the translator's interpretation of the original text, which can significantly impact the direction and depth of the conversive transformation. Additionally, the target audience and their cultural background play a crucial role in shaping how the translation is approached and executed. Furthermore, the linguistic features of both the source and target languages can influence the conversive process, as certain languages may have unique nuances or structures that need to be carefully navigated during translation. Overall, the interplay of these factors underscores the complexity and artistry involved in achieving successful conversive transformations that effectively capture the essence of the original text while resonating with a new audience.

The complexities of literary translation, particularly when dealing with linguistic differences between source and target languages, are illuminated by the insights gleaned from recent studies. The translations of manga from Japanese to Bahasa Melayu/Bahasa Indonesia underscore the importance of profound cultural understanding in addition to linguistic expertise.³ This highlights the inherent challenges of bridging the gap between diverse linguistic and sociocultural

³ Badriyah Yusof et al., 2024

contexts in translation. Moreover, delves into the nuances of artistic translation, emphasizing the concepts of adequacy, equivalence, and the necessity of employing lexical-semantic transformations to navigate the discrepancies between languages. The utilization of translation strategies such as modulation and contextual substitution further exemplifies the intricate process of conveying meaning across linguistic boundaries. These findings underscore the intricate interplay between language, culture, and translation techniques in achieving faithful renditions of literary works across diverse linguistic landscapes.⁴

Furthermore, the impact of conversive transformations in literary translation cannot be understated. These transformations, where the target language text conveys a message opposite to that of the source language, play a crucial role in the reception and interpretation of translated works. While some argue that conversive transformations distort the original intent of the author, others suggest that they add layers of complexity and intrigue to the text, stimulating critical engagement among readers. For example, in the translation of a political satire, a conversive transformation could potentially highlight the absurdity of certain policies or practices more effectively than a literal translation. The decision to employ conversive transformations must thus be carefully considered by translators, balancing fidelity to the original text with the need to convey its underlying themes and messages effectively. Ultimately, these transformations can enrich the reading experience and open up new possibilities for cross-cultural dialogue and understanding.⁵

In conclusion, the conversive transformations observed in literary translation play a crucial role in capturing the essence and voice of the original text while adapting it for a new audience. Through the process of conversive translation, translators navigate the complexities of language, culture, and context to ensure that the integrity of the source text is preserved. By exploring various linguistic

⁴ N. Rybalka et al., 2023

⁵ Laurence Raw, 2012-01-12

and stylistic choices, translators are able to convey the intricacies of the original work in a way that resonates with the target readership. However, it is important to note that while conversive transformations are essential for bridging the gap between languages, they also require a deep understanding of both the source and target cultures. As such, translators must strike a delicate balance between fidelity to the original text and fluency in the target language to create a successful and impactful translation . Moving forward, further research in this area could help shed more light on the intricacies of conversive transformations and contribute to the development of more effective translation strategies.⁶

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